

Assessment Of Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics Among Special Needs Education Students in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed Special needs students' academic performance in Mathematics in Ondo State Special needs schools. It was a qualitative survey of the ex-post facto research design. Previous Mathematics achievement scores of special needs students were collected and collated. The findings of this study revealed that: majority of the special needs students in Ondo State achievement score in Mathematics was above average, there was no significant difference in the achievement scores of hearing impaired and visually impaired students in Mathematics in Ondo State, there was no significant difference in the achievement scores of the visually impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics in Ondo State and there was no statistically significant difference among the achievement scores of visually impaired, hearing impaired and mentally retarded students' in Mathematics in Ondo state. It was concluded that the academic performance of special needs education students in Mathematics was above average and that there was no significant difference amongst the achievement scores of the three categories of Special Needs students in Mathematics in Ondo State. It was therefore recommended that government should recruit more special needs teachers qualified to teach Mathematics in Ondo State special needs schools and provide special mathematical facilities and equipment for effective teaching of special need pupils/students in schools by qualified Special teachers.

Keyword: Assessment, Academic performance, Mathematics, Special needs Education students

Introduction

Education is considered as a germane index to measure societal development. Every nation develops the system of education to express and promote its unique socio-cultural identity and also to meet the challenges of the times. The role of educational development in mitigating several problems of the human society has been realized at all levels. The importance of quality Mathematics education in nation building has also been realized by several nations including developed countries. Thus, improving Mathematics and Science education has been the priority of the policy making agenda (Anon, 2015).

According to Hallahan and Kauffman (2012) Special education is specially designed instruction that meets the unusual needs of an exceptional student. An exceptional student is an individual with a disability or with disabilities. Therefore, it can be stated that Special needs education is the type of education designed to cater for the following type of disabilities: blindness, deafness, and hard of hearing, physical disabilities, mental retardation, speech defects and giftedness. These disabilities require specific types of education, for instance, a blind person would require a Braille machine to read and write, a deaf or hard of hearing person individual would, depending on the magnitude of the disability, need hearing aids or in extreme cases be taught to lip read. The individual with a physical disability would require a wheelchair to help him or her in his or her movement. The mentally challenged individual should be empowered with life skills necessary for survival, such as, reading road signs, manipulating simple mathematical operations, social skills, physical, emotional and cognitive stimulation (Rukuni,2018). Persons with speech difficulties can be assisted by teaching them sign language and interpretation of facial expressions.

The term 'handicapped', 'disabled' and of recent 'exceptionality' have often been used synonymously to describe a condition that deviates or departs from a supposed 'norm'. Such departures from normality, when exhibited by persons, it is considered unusual, inferior, deviant

and abnormal and consequently, abandoned or neglected as incapable. This conclusion is displayed in every facet of our society today against people with exceptional characteristics; education inclusive.

In order to understand these concepts, researchers have shown that while some of these conditions are temporary, others are offshoots or consequences of man's actions and inactions and a few of these are congenital and therefore, permanent. Thus, Yvonne (2016) defined disability as a condition of irregularity, mental weakness or any other disturbance lasting more than six months which hinder a person's integration in the society. However, the Journal of the United Nations (1981) stated that disability is the limitation in an individual's capacity to perform activities which are generally accepted as basic components of daily living such as self-care, social relation and economic activity according to his age, sex and social role as a result of physical or mental functional limitation but also includes the individual's adjustments to this limitation.

The need to educate its disabled population has gained increasing recognition in Nigeria in the last three decades. Interest in the field was aroused by the International Year for Disabled Person (1981), and by the United Nation Declaration of 1983-92 as the Decade of Disabled. Assessment of learning outcomes conducted by teachers could be done using a variety of techniques, such as tests, observations, individual assignments or groups, in order to determine students' competence and level of students' development in Mathematics. Referring to the regulation, assessment is an activity to provide continuous and complete information on the process and results that have been achieved by the students (Clotfelter, Ladd & Vigdor, 2016). In other words, assessment is not carried out only at the end of the period but is carried out in an integrated way by learning activities in the sense that the progress of learning is judged by the process rather than simply the result (Bergström, 2017), while the disability and health fact sheet report of the World Health Organisation (2012) sees disabilities is an umbrella term, covering impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions. Impairment is a problem in body function or structure; an activity limitation is a difficulty encountered by an individual in executing a task or action; while a participation restriction is a problem experienced by an individual in

involvement in life situations. Disability is thus not just a health problem. It is a complex phenomenon, reflecting the interaction between features of a person's body and features of the society in which he or she lives. Overcoming the difficulties faced by people with disabilities requires interventions to remove environmental and social barriers.

Academic performance by students has always been a subject of interest to every educational institution. Whereas there is a consensus that schools should play a major role in this process, there seems to be disagreement about what exactly that role should be. While some believe that the primary focus of schools should be the academic preparation of students (Tienken, & Wilson, 2019). Others however believe that efforts of schools should be integrated with other social institutions such as family and community towards educating children (Huitt, 2017). In fact, heads of educational institution, teachers and parents are primarily responsible for students' academic performance (Darling-Hammond, 2015), and that schools should efficiently and effectively organize them. Meanwhile, on the other hand, the main problem in learning in formal education (school) today is still low absorption of students with Special Needs students (Widodo, 2018). This is evident from the average learning outcomes of the students. This result is certainly the result of learning conditions that are still centered on the teacher and do not touch the realm of special Needs students' own dimensions (Trianto, 2019). The condition is also exacerbated by many Special Needs students who have not yet fully understood the concepts, while the understanding of mathematical concepts is very important (Meyer & Land, 2013; Meltzer, 2012). This may be due to the lack of motivation of the students in the learning of Mathematics, as well as less active participation of the Special needs students in learning of the Mathematics, also in the learning that still uses the model of teaching the lessons (Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012).

Indeed, the understandings of Mathematics lessons require a learning process and learning products or often called learning outcomes. The learning process is systematically done and has a link so that the Special Needs students can master and apply in everyday life. Moreover, in learning Mathematics, Special Needs students not only receive knowledge but are also required to build knowledge with various learning activities, so that learning becomes more meaningful and can be

applied in special needs students' life (Sa'dijah, 2009). Furthermore, the image of the development of Special Needs students learning must be known by the teacher in order to ensure that the students correctly experience the learning process.

There is no exception, the learning of Mathematics in the cube subjects is necessary to activate the Special Needs students skill on how to draw, make networks, realize props to calculate the surface area and the volume of the cube, so that in the subject of the cubes students should have skills to improve Special Needs students' learning outcomes (Gittler & Glück, 2008; Klein, Beman & Smith, 2013). Furthermore, the right strategy for learning and evaluating Mathematics is necessary, so that teachers can measure the results of Special Needs students learning as a whole learning activity. Evaluation is carried out either on the trial or product or students learning result so that all the student's efforts have made an assessment. In this context, assessment becomes one of the solutions for evaluating students during the Mathematics learning process.

Knowledge of Mathematics has often been cited as crucial for several disciplines in higher education, including Technical fields, Engineering, Economics, and Finance, as well as Agriculture, Pharmaceuticals, and Health Sciences (Gradwohl, 2018). Since mathematical knowledge offers widespread application, Special schools in Nigeria require their students to take at least one Mathematics course. Unfortunately, Mathematics in university courses has often been identified as a significant obstacle for Special Needs students (Alenka, 2018). Since poor performance in Mathematics indirectly affects the overall academic performance of students, there is an urgent need to investigate the factors that have contributed to poor performance in Mathematics in special needs schools.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematical skills have long been recognized as essential not only for academic success but also for efficient functioning in everyday life. By studying Mathematics, accuracy, consistency, and mental discipline are trained in Special needs students which are essential skills needed for effective and responsible problem solving and decision making in everyday life. Due

to the global awareness of the importance of mathematical knowledge, on the one hand, and the concern expressed for many years at various levels of education about underachievement in Mathematics, the performance of Special Needs students in Mathematics from primary school to higher education is still a topic of concern; hence, this study;

After reviewing publicly available databases, the researcher found that the majority of studies on mathematical performance and achievement are focused on either primary or secondary education or both. Studies focusing on special schools, which are the subject of this research, are less represented. This study- assessment of Special Needs students' academic performance in Mathematics among Special Needs education students in Ondo State is an attempt to fill this gap.

Purpose of the Study

This study essentially assessed special needs students' academic performance in Mathematics in special needs schools in Ondo State. The study further determined performance of visually impaired and hearing impaired students in Mathematics; and examined the achievement scores of the visually impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics.

Hypotheses

Ho1 There will be no significant difference in the achievement scores of visually impaired and hearing impaired students' in Mathematics.

Ho2 There will be no significant difference in the achievement scores of visually impaired and mentally retarded students' in Mathematics.

Methodology

This study is a qualitative survey of the ex-post facto research design. Previous Mathematics achievement scores (both in external and internal examinations) of special needs students were collected and collated. The population of this study comprised all the students in three special needs schools in Ondo State. These schools are: School for the blind, Owo, Hearing Impaired School, Akure and Mentally Impaired School, Okeigbo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Multiple sampling techniques was used in this study. Purposive sampling was adopted used for the selection of samples for the study which include three special schools: School for the Blind, Owo; School

for the Deaf, Akure and School for the Intellectual Disabilities, Okeigbo. The first two schools were selected because of the students involvement in internal and external examinations while the Intellectual disabilities/mentally retarded school, Okeigbo's students do not participate in external examinations but internal assessment hence intact sampling technique was employed on their own basis which means that the entire pupils/students of a particular academic session were considered for the study without exemption. Achievement scores, mean test scores were derived from students' records in Mathematics from two academic sessions in both external and internal examinations. Demographic data formed the first part of the instrument which contains the school, gender and status. While achievement scores of respondents in Mathematics which were collected and collated to find out students' academic performances in Mathematics among the special needs participants formed the second part of the instrument. The instrument face and content validity have been ascertained and attested to by Ondo State Ministry of Education. Internal consistency was the achievement scores of the respondents ascertained by comparing the performance of respondents in external examination with that of the internal examination. Written informed consent was sought from the various Head teachers of the three special schools involved in the study. Data was collated and collected from the Registrar of each of the school with the aid of research assistant.

Results

Table1: Performance level of the hearing impaired, visually impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics Ondo State Special schools.

Description		Frequency	Percentage	Total
Special Needs students	Deaf	191	81.6%	234(100%)
	Blind	23	9.8%	
	Mentally Retarded	20	8.5%	
Grade	0-39 Fail	27	11.5%	234(100%)
	40-49 Pass	54	23.1%	
	50-69 Credit	108	46.2%	
	70-100 Distinction	45	19.2%	

Source: Field survey reports, 2021 Ministry of Education.

The result in Table 1 shows that 81.6% of the special needs students in this study had hearing impairment, 9.8% were visually impaired while 8.5% were mentally retarded. It further reveals that 11.5% of the special needs students failed Mathematics, 23.1% passed Mathematics, and 46.2% had credit while 19.2% had distinctions in Mathematics. It could be inferred that 65.4% of the special needs students in Ondo State achievement scores in Mathematics was above average. Majority had at least credit passes in Mathematics while 34.6% performed below average in their Mathematics performance.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of visually impaired and hearing impaired students in mathematics in special needs schools.

Table 2: summary of the differences in mathematics achievement scores of the deaf and blind students.

Variable		N	Mean	SD	T	DF	Sig	Decision
Grade	Deaf	191	2.7120	0.9436	1.208	212	0.228	Not significant
	Blind	2	2.9565	0.6381				

P<0.05

The result in table 2 shows that the t-test value was not significant ($t = 1.208$, $df = 212$, $p = 0.228$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant difference in the achievement score of hearing impaired and visually impaired students in Mathematics in Ondo State was accepted ($p > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of Visually Impaired and Mentally Retarded students in Mathematics.

Table 3: Summary showing the differences in mathematics achievement scores of visually impaired and mentally impaired students.

Special Needs		N	Mean	SD	T	DF	Sig	Decision
Grade	Blind	23	2.9565	0.63800	1.453	41	0.154	Not significant
	Mental retarded	20	2.6500	0.74516				

P<0.05

The t-test result in the Table 3 reveals the mean achievement scores of visually impaired students in Mathematics to be 2.9565 while the mean achievement score of the mentally retarded students in Mathematics to be 2.65. The result further shows that the t-test value of 1.453 was not statistically significant ($df = 41$, $P = 0.154$). Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the achievement score of visually impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of hearing impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics.

Table 4: summary showing the difference in Mathematics achievement scores of hearing impaired and mentally retarded students.

Special Needs		N	Mean	SD	T	DF	Sig	Decision
Grade	Blind	191	2.7120	0.94357	0.285	209	0.776	Not significant
	Mental retarded	20	2.6500	0.74516				

P<0.05

The result in Table 4 shows that the t-test value was not significant at 0.05 probability level ($t= 0.285$, $df =209$, $p =0.776$). Therefore, the research hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of hearing impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics was accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference amongst achievement scores of visually impaired and mentally impaired students in Mathematics.

Table5: ANOVA showing significant difference among the achievement scores of Visually Impaired, Hearing impaired and Mentally Retarded students in Mathematics.

Grade	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig	Decision
Between Groups	1.370	2	0.685	0.838	0.434	Not significant
Within Groups	188.669	231	0.817			
Total	190.038	233				

P<0.05

The Analysis of variance in Table 5 shows that there was no statistically significant difference among the achievement scores of visually impaired, hearing impaired and mentally retarded students in Mathematics ($df = 2,231$; $F = 0.838$; $p = 0.434$).

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The results in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 shows that the Mathematics achievement scores of special needs students in Ondo State special schools was above average. This shows that every factor necessary for the academic performance of the students must have been supplied such as students' effort/persistence, academic ambition, previous grades, parents' education, parents academic ambition for their wards (Sentamu, 2003; Osiki, 2001) sex of the child, age of students (Aripin, Mahmood, Rohaizad, Yeop, & Anuar, 2008), peer influence (Tope, 2011; Black, 2002); influenced their performance. This study is in line with the above researchers' positions.

In addition, from the results, it could be inferred that the special needs students' attitude toward Mathematics is positive. The study's outcomes is also in agreement with the submissions of Hijazi and Naqvi (2016). Hijazi and Naqvi (2016) remark that academic performance is a multidimensional construct composed of the skills, attitudes, and behaviours of a learner that contribute to academic success in the classroom.

Conclusion

It was deduced in the study that learning Mathematics by the special needs students will not allow them to express any year of dropping out of the school because of the fearful nature of the subject, also their handicapping conditions did not prevent them from learning mathematics adequately. It was also observed that lack of motivation of the special Needs students in the learning of mathematics as well as less active participation of the students in learning of Mathematics without the use of mathematical tools needed by these Special students while some teachers still use the old model style of teaching during classes for poor academic performance. Also, mathematical skills with various learning activities must have been built since students do not only receive knowledge but they are also required to build knowledge with various learning activities, so that learning becomes more meaningful and can be applied in student's life. The study also indicated that special needs students often attain greater achievement scores in Mathematics in using mathematical tools such as Abacus, Taylor frame etc. Based on the findings of this study;

it was concluded that the academic performance of special needs education students in Mathematics in Ondo State was above average and that there was no difference amongst the achievement attainment of the three categories of special needs students in Mathematics in Ondo State.

Recommendations

- The government should recruit more special needs teachers qualified to teach Mathematics in Ondo State special needs schools.
- There is also an urgent need to provide special mathematical facilities and equipment for special needs schools, teachers and pupils/students; such like drill age machine, mathematical kits like Taylor's frame, constructional kit, Perkins braille and abacus.
- Provision of guidance and counselling to the special students is vital to help encourage their love for Mathematics and to prepare them for life in the larger society.
- Special needs students should be provided with adequate living kits and a well-constructed and adequate living environment as this will enable them to concentrate more when learning Mathematics.
- Senior secondary schools should be built for the special needs students within Ondo State and the Mathematics Curriculum to be taught them should be tailored towards Mathematics for daily living.
- Government of Ondo State and stakeholders should ensure that they make provision for special needs students a viable education within the State. This will serve as motivation to the special needs students to want to pass Mathematics because it is a requirement for tertiary education.

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